

MUSICOLOGY

THE VOCAL ART OF YASHAR GURBANOV

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Abstract

Azerbaijani vocal art stands, as a testament to the country's profound cultural heritage, intertwining centuries of tradition, emotion, and artistic expression. Central to this rich vocal tradition is **Mugham** - a sophisticated and emotive form of music that integrates poetry, instrumental mastery, and vocal improvisation. Alongside Mugham, **Ashiq** music, performed by the storytelling musicians known as Ashiq, adds another layer of depth with its narrative songs and rich folklore. These vocal forms are not only pivotal to Azerbaijan's cultural identity but have also garnered global recognition. As we delve deeper into the intricacies and contemporary relevance of Azerbaijani vocal art, we uncover a world where ancient traditions meet modern influences, creating a unique fusion that continues to captivate and inspire. Yashar Gurbanov is a name that resonates deeply within Azerbaijani vocal art. Known for his talent and dedication to preserving and promoting the rich musical traditions of his homeland, Gurbanov has become a leading figure in classical and folk music. His contributions span across performances, recordings, and educational efforts, making him one of the pivotal characters in the cultural landscape of Azerbaijan. This article examines the work of Yashar Gurbanov, who has a special role in the promotion of Azerbaijani vocal art, which resonates far beyond the borders of Azerbaijan with its historical roots and artistic nuances.

Keywords: art, vocal art, Yashar Gurbanov, Estrada, concerto, voice, classic music.

Throughout history, Azerbaijani vocal art experienced significant transformation and development, shaped by the socio-political changes of the time. While mugham remained a cornerstone of the national musical identity, other vocal art forms flourished too, reflecting the ideological and cultural shifts.

In the Soviet period, state-sponsored initiatives aimed at preserving and promoting folk traditions led to the establishment of folk music ensembles and choirs. These groups often performed re-arranged traditional songs to align with Soviet artistic principles, emphasizing harmony and collective performance over individual expression. The influence of Soviet culture brought about the rise of **Estrada**, a genre of Soviet popular music that combined elements of folk, classical, and contemporary styles. Azerbaijani singers like Rashid Behbudov and Muslim Magomayev became prominent figures in this genre. Their performances, characterized by powerful vocals and theatrical presentations, gained widespread popularity within Azerbaijan and abroad.

This period saw the incorporation of Azerbaijani language, themes, and motifs into Soviet-style compositions, creating a unique hybrid that reflected both local traditions and Soviet modernity. The Soviet era also brought about significant advancements in music education and professionalization. Conservatories and music schools were established, providing systematic training for aspiring vocalists and musicians. These institutions played a vital role in nurturing a new generation of artists who would carry Azerbaijani vocal traditions into the future. Beyond the enduring tradition of Mugham, other vocal forms

evolved, influenced by both local heritage and Soviet cultural policies. The legacy of this era is a rich tapestry of classical, folk, and popular music that continues to shape Azerbaijan's musical landscape today.

Born in a region steeped in musical heritage, Yashar Gurbanov was exposed to the sounds and rhythms of Azerbaijani music from an early age. His journey into the world of vocal art began with traditional folk songs, which are deeply ingrained in the culture of Azerbaijan. These early experiences shaped his understanding of music and laid the foundation for his future endeavors. Azerbaijani vocal performance has become an independent art of performing precisely by benefiting from the art of ashig and mugham. The essence of the Azerbaijani national classical vocal art is based on the creativity of Uzeyir Hajibeyov. On January 21, 1908, the vocal parts in the opera "Leyli and Majnun" by U. Hajibeyov - arias, ariosos, duets, and choral scenes - performed by the opera troupe in Baku had a great impact on the development of mass vocal performance art in Azerbaijan. As in all regions of Azerbaijan, in Nakhchivan, it is necessary to mention the great service of local ashig and singing masters in the creation of a vocal school. The cultural environment in Baku played a special role in the development of Azerbaijani vocal art. It is here that the formation of the school of composition, formed by Ü. Hajibeyli, which includes features characteristic of classical European music, also influenced the development of vocal art. Since the first decades of the 20th century, a vocal school, which is the bearer of new principles has been established in Baku. Among the students of this school are Nakhchivan vocalists.

Poster of the concert dedicated to 70-year jubilee of Yashar Gurbanov.

Yashar Gurbanov is one of the first vocalists of the Nakhchivan vocal performance school, who received vocal education in Baku and worked there in Sumgayit. Yashar Gurbanov was born on May 22, 1954, in Sumgait city. He received his first education at secondary school No. 4 in Sumgait city.

Gurbanov's formal training in music began at a prestigious institution where he honed his skills under the tutelage of renowned masters. His education encompassed a broad spectrum of musical styles, from classical folk songs - a traditional Azerbaijani genre characterized by complex improvisation and deep emotional expression - to contemporary compositions. This diverse training allowed Gurbanov to develop a versatile and nuanced vocal style.

In the years 1961-1971, when he was studying, he was one of the active members of the school's self-activity collective, he was a participant in many concerts, not only in Azerbaijan but also in Ukraine and Russia. Here, he was an active member of many pop groups. Among them, we can mention the popular pop collectives of N. Narimanov club "Romashka", "Rovesnik" of BTZ club, "Shakhmat" club, "Stroitel", Vishnyakov, and "Ashiqlar". Yashar Gurbanov started his musical career at the age of 14. His close relationships with artists such as Elbrus Mehdiyev, Yashar Safarov, and Novruz Mammadov greatly influenced and benefited his musical development. His influences are varied, drawing inspiration from both historical figures in Azerbaijani music and contemporary artists. The rich tapestry of sounds that defines Gurbanov's music is a testament to his ability to blend tradition with innovation seamlessly.

In 1971, he moved to Nakhchivan city with his family and continued his activities there. Here he was invited to work as a soloist in the Nakhchivan State Song and Dance Ensemble. In the years 1973-1976, he was in active military service and did not stop his musical activities. He created a variety group on the ship he served and performed in many concerts, even in Tunisia, Egypt, and Algeria with extensive concert programs. The main place in his repertoire is our folk song

"Sari Gelin". Yashar Gurbanov performed this song in almost all his concerts. After completing his military service, Yashar Gurbanov returned to Nakhchivan, where he continued his musical career in the Nakhchivan State Song and Dance Ensemble. In 1978, to continue his education, he was admitted to the Nakhchivan Secondary Music School, majoring in vocal. He studied vocal at a professional level in the class of Olga Ivanovna, a specialist pedagogue from St. Petersburg, and also took master classes from her. He graduated from that school in 1982. In 1987, he was admitted to the Azerbaijan State Art University, and in 1992 he successfully graduated. During his studies, he performed in many concert programs and acquired a rich repertoire. Here, T. Guliyev, R. Hajiyev, P. Bulbuloglu, M. Magomayev, R. Mirishli, and Pakhmutova performed popular Russian pop works and arias, romances, and songs of many foreign composers and continues to teach students. He was invited by R. Babayev, head of the Azerbaijan TV variety symphony orchestra, to the Song Theater created by Rashid Behbudov, but he could not go due to his family situation. In 1981, he was invited to a concert program organized by the Nakhchivan Komsomol Organization, to be held in Moscow. The tour does not end only in Moscow, but also in Krasnoyarsk, Novosibirsk, and other cities. A month-long musical tour ends very successfully. Although Yashar Gurbanov occasionally stopped his stage activities, he did not stop his teaching activities from 1978 until today. As a result of his activities, he was awarded the medal "Otlichnik kulturnogo peyvstva nad selom" by the Ministry of Culture of the USSR, I degree diplomas at many festivals ("Golden Autumn" festivals held in Khankendi (1980-1983)). The music schools of the Babek region of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic have achieved great achievements in the training of personnel, as their students were awarded 1st-degree diplomas in the competitions dedicated to the birthday of Azerbaijani National Leader Heydar Aliyev. Among them, Habib Huseynov, Samir Farajov and others can be mentioned. He is currently working as a teacher at the Nakhchivan Music College, teaching vocal art and

the secrets of his art to the young generation, training future vocal performers, and at the same time working as a soloist of the Nakhchivan State Philharmonic. The personnel trained by him continued their musical activities in various concert halls and were awarded honorary titles. He performed concert programs at state events held in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic and was awarded many times. On September 18, 2016, Yashar Gurbanov was awarded the title of Honored Artist of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

Yashar Gurbanov's vocal technique is marked by its clarity, emotional depth, and technical precision. His ability to convey the subtleties of Azerbaijani folk songs has earned him widespread acclaim. Gurbanov's mastery of this art form is evident in his performances, where his voice effortlessly navigates complex melodic patterns, creating a captivating auditory experience. These pieces, often characterized by their lyrical beauty and rhythmic diversity, showcase his ability to adapt his vocal technique to different styles while maintaining the integrity of the music. Gurbanov's contributions to Azerbaijani music extend beyond his performances. He is actively involved in efforts to preserve and promote the country's musical heritage. Through recordings, he has created a valuable archive of traditional songs, ensuring that they are accessible to future generations. His educational initiatives, including workshops and masterclasses, have inspired and nurtured a new generation of musicians, fostering a renewed interest in Azerbaijani vocal art.

Yashar Gurbanov's music has transcended national boundaries, earning him recognition on the international stage. His performances at global music festivals and collaborations with artists from different cultural backgrounds have introduced Azerbaijani music

to a broader audience. Through these endeavors, Gurbanov has showcased the beauty of his homeland's musical traditions and highlighted the universal language of music.

As a custodian of Azerbaijani vocal art, Yashar Gurbanov continues to explore new horizons while remaining deeply rooted in tradition. His work embodies the spirit of Azerbaijani music - rich, diverse, and ever-evolving. With each performance and project, he contributes to a living legacy that celebrates the past, embraces the present, and inspires the future.

In the world of music, few artists manage to achieve the delicate balance between honoring tradition and embracing innovation. Yashar Gurbanov is one such artist, and his vocal art is a testament to the enduring power and beauty of Azerbaijani music. As he continues to share his gift with the world, Yashar Gurbanov remains a beacon of cultural pride and artistic excellence.

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